

ENHANCED DAMPING PROPERTIES OF GRAPHENE/NICKEL FOAM FILLED EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Graphene, Nickel foam, Epoxy, Nanocomposites, Damping

ABSTRACT

In order to obtain high-performance composites with high stiffness and high damping properties, we prepared three-dimensional graphene/nickel foam reinforced epoxy composites, and investigated its viscoelastic behaviour and damping characteristics. In this work, the 3D graphene foam was obtained by growing graphene onto porous nickel foam by using chemical vapour deposition method, and the obtained graphene/Ni hybrid foams were used as reinforcing fillers, and subsequently graphene/Ni filled epoxy composites were prepared by using a vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding technique. The static and dynamic mechanical behaviour of the graphene/Ni/epoxy composites were measured. We found that the graphene/Ni hybrid foam exhibited higher compressive modulus and larger energy dissipation than the neat Ni foam, which is mainly attributed to good interfacial bonding between graphene and nickel substrates. Furthermore, we found that the graphene layers existing between Ni substrate and epoxy matrix played an important role in enhancing the damping properties of the graphene/Ni/epoxy composites. The rich and flexible graphene interfaces existing in the nanocomposites can greatly increase interfacial friction between fillers and matrix during deformation, consequently resulting in large energy dissipation and high damping capability. Therefore, the graphene/Ni/epoxy composites with high damping have great potential to be used widely in many fields.